

**R J Tibrewal Commerce College
Vastrapur, Ahmedabad 380 015 (Gujarat)**

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**Universities Commerce &
Management Teachers' Association
(Gujarat State)**

**NATIONAL CONFERENCE
ON
SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN BUSINESS
ALONG WITH SOCIETAL CHANGES**

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Vastrapur, Ahmedabad 380 018 (Gujarat)

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Volume 1

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IMPACT OF FINANCIAL LEVERAGE ON PROFITABILITY OF FMCG AND ELECTRONICS COMPANIES

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ABSTRACT:

The purpose of this research is to study and understand the effect of financial leverage on the profitability of FMCG and Electronic Companies over a period of 10 years. (2009-2018) for 5 selected companies. These research has employed 3 independent variable(Debt-Equity ratio, Interest Coverage ratio, Debt asset ratio) as a measure of financial leverage and 1 dependent variable(Return on asset) as a measure of financial performance. The analysis of the result show that Debt equity ratio and debt asset ratio is having a negative relationship whereas interest coverage ratio is having a positive relationship with Return on Asset (ROA).Based on these the researcher recommend that the firm should have the optimal level of debt finance so as to ensure the optimal utilisation of firms assets and the management should also monitor the interest charged on debt financing so as to avoid the liquidity problem.

Key Words: Financial Leverage, Financial Performance, FMCG Sector, Electronic Sector, Multiple regression, Debt Equity ratio, Interest Coverage Ratio, Return on Assets, Financial Statements.

I. Introduction

A firm can make use of alternative sources of finance which are having different costs. Some have a fixed bearing rate of return(Debentures and Preference capital) while some are having varying rate of return(Equity share capital).Leverage is the employment of an asset/sources of funds for which firm pays a fixed rate of return. What level of debt should a firm employ in order to have optimal utilisation of asset is a question which every researcher wants to know. If the firm is employing high debt, it means that there is more risk to the outsiders as the availability of margin of safety of the funds is very less while if the firm is employing lower debt than the benefit of trading on equity is not much available to the owners of the firm. So the firm should try to keep its capital structure at an optimal level.

II. Theoretical Framework

Khushbakht T.(2013) has examined that degree of financial leverage is having a positive relationship with ROA while degree of operating leverage is having a negative relationship with ROA.At the end the researcher has concluded that there is no significant effect of operating and financial leverage on ROA,ROE,ROI and EPS.

Enekwe, C., Chinedu, I., Agu, Charles, I., & Eziedo, K. (2014) examined that debt equity ratio and total debt ratio is having a negative relationship with ROA while interest coverage ratio is having a positive relationship with ROA.In these study it was concluded that none of the selected independent variable is having a significant impact on the profitability of the company.

III. Objectives of the study:

- 1) To measure the effect of Interest Coverage ratio on the profitability of the selected FMCG and Electronics Company.
- 2) To measure the effect of Debt Equity ratio on the profitability of the selected FMCG and Electronics Company.
- 3) To measure the effect of Debt Asset ratio on the profitability of selected FMCG and Electronics Company.

IV. Scope

Basically there are two types of leverage:

- 1) **Operating Leverage:** Operating leverage can be defined as the as the firms' ability to utilize the fixed operating cost in order to understand the effect of changes in sales on earnings before interest and tax.
- 2) **Financial leverage:** Financial leverage relates to the financing activities of a firm. The firm can raise the funds from different sources. Some having a fixed rate of return and some having a variations in return. Financial leverage refers to the ability of the firm to use the fixed financial charges in order to magnify the impact of changes in earnings before interest and tax on earnings per share.

There is one another variation of leverage i.e. **combined leverage** (combination of operating leverage and financial leverage). It measure the overall effect of fixed operating cost and fixed financial charges on the profit available to the equity shareholders. As far as these study is concerned the researcher has undertaken the research study for financial leverage.

V. Sample Design:

Sampling Techniques:

This study is related to FMCG and Electronics Company. The ex-post facto research is being used in these research as it involves the events which has already taken place and it can't be manipulated.

Sample Size:

The selected sample is based on 3 FMCG Company for a period of 10 years and 2 Electronic Company for a period of 10 years.

The name of the selected companies are mentioned below:

- 1) ITC Ltd.
- 2) Videocon Industries Ltd.
- 3) Dabur India Ltd.
- 4) Britannia Ltd.
- 5) Bajaj Electricals Ltd.

Data Collection method:

Entire data is collected from the financial statements of the selected companies available on official websites.

Data Analysis Method:

The data is analysed by calculating Descriptive statistics, Correlation Coefficients and Regression. The software used to analyse the above research study is MS EXCEL 13.

Time Period of the study:

Data for the period(2009-2018) is used for the purpose of these research study.

Limitations of the study:

1. These study is purely based on secondary data and time period taken is of 10 years only.
2. More variables as a measure of calculating financial performance and financial leverage can be taken into account.
3. Apart from these there are various external factors which are having an impact on the profitability of the firm.

VI. Selection and Description of the variables:

Total 4 variables are considered in these research study to analyse the effect of financial leverage on the profitability of the company.

1) Interest Coverage Ratio:

These ratio measures the debt servicing capacity of a firm with regards to fixed interest on long term loans is concerned. These ratio indicates the extent to which a fall in EBIT is tolerable in such a way that the ability of the firm to service its interest payments would not be adversely effected.

It is calculated as:

Interest coverage ratio= $\text{EBIT}/\text{Interest}$.

2) Debt equity ratio:

These ratio measures the ratio of borrowed funds and owners funds to have a view of the long-term solvency of a firm. These ratio reflects the individual claims of creditors and shareholders on the total assets of the firm. High ratio indicates more risk to the creditors and vice versa.

It is calculated as:

Debt Equity ratio: $\text{Total Debt}/\text{Shareholders funds}$

3) Debt Asset Ratio:

These ratio measure the amount of assets that are being financed by outsiders. High ratio indicates that majority of assets are financed by the outsiders and thus it creates more risk to the outsiders. Whereas a low ratio indicates that most are the assets are being financed through owners' funds and thereby providing security to the creditors.

It is calculated as:

Debt Asset ratio- $\text{Total Debt}/\text{Total Assets}$

4) Return on assets:

These ratio is used to measure the profitability of the firm. Here the profitability is measured in terms of the relationship between net profits and assets. With an increase in the debt, there is an increase in the amount of the interest to be paid and as a result the profitability of the company is affected and as a result in these research study in order to know the effect on profitability, interest coverage ratio, debt equity ratio and debt asset ratio are considered.

It is calculated as:

Return on asset: Profit before tax/Total Assets

VII. Formulation of hypothesis:

H₀: There is no significant effect of interest coverage ratio on Return on assets of selected FMCG and Electronics Company.

H₀: There is no significant effect of Debt Equity ratio on Return on assets of selected FMCG and Electronics Company.

H₀: There is no significant effect of Debt Asset ratio on Return on assets of selected FMCG and Electronics Company.

VIII. Methodology

Firstly descriptive statistics was applied to describe the relevant aspects of financial leverage and provide detailed information about each relevant variable used as a measure of financial leverage. Correlation was used to know the direction of relationship between different variables which are used in these research study while regression analysis was used to know the effect of selected independent variable on profitability of selected companies.

The model used was multiple regressions which is described as follows:

$$Y = b_0 + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + \dots + E_i$$

Where,

Y=Dependent variable of company

X=Independent variable of company

B₀=Intercept for X variable of selected company

B₁,B₂,B₃= Coefficient for independent variable X₁,X₂,X₃ respectively

E_i=Error term

Fitting the above model into these research study the model is as follows:

$$(ROA)_{yt} = b_0 + b_1(DER)_{yt} + b_2(ICR)_{yt} + b_3(DAR)_{yt} + E_i$$

Where, ROA=Return on assets

ICR=Interest Coverage ratio

DER=Debt Equity Ratio

DAR=Debt Asset Ratio

E_i=Error term

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Particulars	Mean	Standard deviation	N
ROA	13.49	9.37	50.00
Interest Coverage ratio	124.97	250.13	50.00
Debt Equity ratio	0.64	1.03	50.00
Debt Asset Ratio	112.17	112.85	50.00

Explanation

The descriptive statistics shows that over the period under study in which financial leverage measured by interest coverage ratio, debt equity ratio and debt asset ratio. The mean ranges from 0.64 for Debt Equity ratio to 124.97 for Interest Coverage ratio. The value of mean and standard deviation are highest for interest coverage ratio which suggests that the data is widely dispersed.

Table 2: Correlation

Correlation	ROA	Interest Coverage Ratio	Debt Equity Ratio	Debt Asset Ratio
ROA	1.00	-	-	-
Interest Coverage Ratio.	0.56	1.00	-	-
Debt Equity Ratio	-0.67	-0.31	1.00	-
Debt Asset	-0.47	-0.27	0.56	1.00

Explanation

The correlation matrix indicates that interest coverage ratio is having a positive relationship with ROA while debt equity ratio and Debt Asset ratio is having a negative relationship with ROA which implies that financial performance degrades with increase in debt. It was also observed that Interest coverage ratio is having negative relationship with debt equity ratio and debt asset ratio while debt asset ratio is having a positive relationship debt equity ratio.

Table 3: Multiple Regression

Regression Statistics	Value
Multiple R	0.76
R Square	0.58
Adjusted R Square	0.55
Standard Error	6.30
Observations	50.00

Summary Output

ANOVA

	Df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
Regression	3.00	2471.75	823.92	20.76	0.00
Residual	46.00	1825.84	39.69		
Total	49.00	4297.58			

	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value	Lower 95%	Upper 95%	Lower 95.0%	Upper 95.0%
Intercept	15.51	1.47	10.55	7.17E- 14	12.55	18.47	12.55	18.47
X Variable 1(significant)(Debt equity)	-4.32	1.05	-4.13	0.0002	-6.42	-2.21	-6.42	-2.21
X Variable 2(significant)(Interest coverage)	0.01	0.00	3.78	0.0005	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.02
X Variable 3(not significant)(debt asset ratio)	-0.01	0.01	-0.98	0.3341	-0.03	0.01	-0.03	0.01

Level of significance=5%

Explanation

From the above table we can see that the value of R^2 is 58% i.e. only 58% of the variation in the return on assets is been explained by the chosen independent variable (debt equity ratio, interest coverage ratio, debt asset ratio) while the rest 42% of the variation is been caused due to other factors. Moreover the adjusted R^2 is 55% which suggests that R^2 is highly inflated. The value of intercept from the above table is 15.51 which suggests that even if all the independent variable are kept constant ROA would be 15.51%. The regression coefficient for all the independent variables are -4.32, 0.01 and -0.01 respectively which denotes the slope of each and every independent variable. The t value for debt equity ratio is $-4.13 < 2$ which suggest that debt equity ratio is having significant impact on ROA of the selected companies. These analysis is also supported by p-value which is < 0.05 . The t value for interest coverage ratio is $3.78 < 2$ which suggest that interest coverage ratio is having significant impact on ROA of the selected companies. These analysis is strengthened by p-value which is < 0.05 . The t value for debt asset ratio is $-0.98 < 2$ which suggest that debt asset ratio is not having significant impact on ROA of the selected companies. These analysis is also supported by p-value which is > 0.05 . Here the F-value is 20.76 with a p-value < 0.05 which suggests that the model is significantly fit and hence the null hypothesis should be rejected.

IX. Conclusion

This paper explained the study on the impact of financial leverage on the profitability of the selected companies. Data was collected from the annual reports of the selected companies from different websites for a period of 10 years. Return on assets was taken as a dependent variable and interest coverage ratio, debt equity ratio, debt asset ratio were taken as independent variable. After conducting correlation and multiple regression analysis it was found that debt equity ratio and interest coverage ratio is having a significant impact on the profitability of the selected companies whereas debt asset ratio is not having any significant effect on the profitability on the company. Hence we can conclude that only with the change in debt equity ratio and interest coverage ratio there is a change in the profitability of the company.

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